

Exploring Behavioral Duality in Real Life and Cyberspace as Perceived in Oneself and in Others: A Comparative Study

Frederick Edward Fabella

Ph. D., FEUR Graduate School, Cainta, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This quantitative study attempted to explore whether there is a variation in the respondents' perception of the practice of **positive relationship behaviors, negative relationship behaviors, introverted behaviors and extroverted behaviors in real life and online. Self-discrepancy theory was employed as the framework. Two sets of participants were utilized. The first set rated their own behavior while the second set rated the behavior of others in general. Both sets were asked whether these behaviors were perceived to be practiced in the same degree in real life and online or if they perceive them being practiced more in one or the other. The findings indicate that both sets of respondents rated most of the behaviors as being practiced more in real life, which supports the assertion of the self-discrepancy theory that people may attempt to reconstruct themselves differently in cyberspace.**

INTRODUCTION

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, which resulted in more people being unable to leave their homes, individuals have been spending much of their lives in cyberspace. [1]

As early as 2018, a survey of more than 600 social media users yielded that nearly everyone (86%) uses social media at least once a day, and 72% use it multiple times in the same period. Majority use Facebook (82%), YouTube (75%), and Instagram (53%) at least once a week. [2]

When Pew Research Center began tracking social media usage in 2005, just 5% of American adults used at least one of these platforms. But by 2011 that percentage had risen to half of all Americans, and today 72% of the public uses some form of social media.[3]

According to another survey, the following are the top ten reasons why people use social media: 1. To stay in touch with what friends are doing (42%), 2. To stay up-to-date with news and current events (41%), 3. To fill up spare time (39%), 4. To find funny or entertaining content (37%), 5. General networking with other people (34%), 6. Because friends are already on them (33%), 7. To share photos or videos with others (32%), 8. To share my opinion (30%), 9. To research new products to buy (29%), 10. To meet new people (27%).[4]

The Internet can change the interaction of people and how they communicate. The online world allows individuals to reconstruct their cyber identity partially or entirely different from their real identity. A study utilizing the self-discrepancy theory investigated virtual identity reconstruction and user satisfaction. Based on the data obtained from 357 social network users, a significant positive relationship between online identity reconstruction and user satisfaction was found. [5]

Self-discrepancy theory asserts that people have an 'ought', 'ideal', and 'actual' self. The ideal self is the person one would like to become, the ought self is the person one thinks they should be and the actual self is who one truly thinks one is. This theory further states that all of these are valid selves. Therefore, people may "use" social media as a reminder of their ideal self or ought self, or to possibly explore different roles in ways that are not apparent in face-to-face communication.[6]

The objective of this study was to ascertain whether people perceive behaviors as varying between real life and in cyberspace/online. The following four types of behavior were studied: positive relationship behaviors, negative relationship behaviors, introverted behaviors and extroverted behaviors.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions: (1) How do the respondents rate themselves in positive relationship behaviors, negative relationship behaviors, introverted behaviors and extroverted behaviors in their practice in real life and online? (2) How do the respondents rate other people in general in terms of these same behaviors in their practice in real life and online? (3) Is there a significant difference between how the respondents see their own behavior and how they see the behavior of other people with respect to questions 1 and 2?

METHODOLOGY

A 40-item, researcher-made instrument which underwent content validation was created using words that describe four types of behaviors namely, positive relationship behaviors (10 items), negative relationship behaviors (10 items), introverted behaviors (10 items) and extroverted behaviors (10 items). [7] The instrument utilized a 5-point Likert scale.

To ascertain whether the respondents perceive a variation in the practice of such behaviors in real life or online, each participant rated an item as being practiced “a great deal more in real life”, “slightly more in real life”, “generally the same in real life and online”, “slightly more online” or “a great deal more online.” These possible responses were assigned Likert values of -2, -1, 0, 1 and 2, respectively. The weighted mean for each item was then computed.

Adults whose ages ranged from 18 to 43 and residing in Rizal (San Mateo and Rodriguez), Marikina City, Quezon City and Antipolo City in the Philippines were invited to volunteer as respondents. Google forms were created in order that these respondents could answer the researcher-made instrument online.

The respondents were divided into set A and set B. 126 respondents (99 females and 27 males) comprised Set A and were asked to rate how they (self) perceive the practice of such behaviors in real life and online. On the other hand, 114 respondents (90 females and 24 males) comprising Set B were asked to rate how they perceive other people’s practice of such in real life or online.

Table 1 shows the scale of interpretation used for the weighted means for each item.

Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 show the weighted means computed for each item for Set A respondents who rated themselves and Set B respondents who rated other people in general.

Tables 6, 7, 8 and 9 indicate the degree of statistical difference between Set A and Set B’s responses.

RESULTS

Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
-2.0000000 to -1.2000001	A great deal more in real life
-1.2000000 to -0.4000001	Slightly more in real life
-0.4000000 to 0.4000000	Generally the same in real life and online
0.4000001 to 1.2000000	Slightly more online
1.2000001 to 2.0000000	A great deal more online

Item	Set A’s Perception of <i>of Self</i>		Set B’s Perception of <i>Others</i>	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. In showing selfless concern	-0.6111111	Slightly more in real life	-0.3893805	Generally the same in real life and online
2. In showing a desire to help	-0.7857143	Slightly more in real life	-0.4513274	Slightly more in real life
3. In showing sympathy/concern	-0.452381	Slightly more in real life	-0.2389381	Generally the same in real life and online
4. In thinking of other people	-0.6984127	Slightly more in real life	-0.5575221	Slightly more in real life

5. In being loyal	-0.8492063	Slightly more in real life	-0.619469	Slightly more in real life
6. In giving fair and equal treatment	-0.5555556	Slightly more in real life	-0.300885	Generally the same in real life and online
7. In being kind	-0.6031746	Slightly more in real life	-0.6283186	Slightly more in real life
8. In being pleasant	-0.5873016	Slightly more in real life	-0.4424779	Slightly more in real life
9. In being polite	-0.484127	Slightly more in real life	-0.7079646	Slightly more in real life
10. In being sincere	-0.7063492	Slightly more in real life	-0.8672566	Slightly more in real life
Grand weighted mean	-0.6333333	Slightly more in real life	-0.520354	Slightly more in real life

Table 3. Negative Relationship Behaviors

Item	Set A's Perception of <i>Self</i>		Set B's Perception of <i>Others</i>	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
11. In being intimidating	-0.1904762	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.4070796	Slightly more in real life
12. In arguing	-0.0714286	Generally the same in real life and online	0.3362832	Generally the same in real life and online
13. In being bossy and telling people what to do	-0.1269841	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.4778761	Slightly more in real life
14. In telling people things to make them do what they want	-0.1507937	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.2831858	Generally the same in real life and online
15. In trying to control other people	0.1190476	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.3628319	Generally the same in real life and online
16. In being unstable and unreliable	0.5396825	Slightly more online	0.0973451	Generally the same in real life and online
17. In not caring about other people or their feelings	0.5952381	Slightly more online	0.0619469	Generally the same in real life and online
18. In trying to influence other people	-0.3492063	Generally the same in real life and online	0.4955752	Slightly more online
19. In being rude and breaking social rules	0.4126984	Slightly more online	0.2035398	Generally the same in real life and online
20. In seeking revenge when they do not get what they want from other people	0.4126984	Slightly more online	-0.2920354	Generally the same in real life and online
Grand weighted mean	0.1190476	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.0628319	Generally the same in real life and online

Table 4. Introverted Behaviors

Item	Set A's Perception of of Self		Set B's Perception of Others	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
21. In being cautious and reserved	-0.4603175	Slightly more in real life	-1.0088496	Slightly more in real life
22. In preferring not to socialize with other people	-0.1190476	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.8230088	Slightly more in real life
23. In being independent-minded and doing what they want	-0.7619048	Slightly more in real life	-0.7168142	Slightly more in real life
24. In engaging in deep thought	-0.9761905	Slightly more in real life	-0.9823009	Slightly more in real life
25. In not revealing their thoughts easily	-0.6428571	Slightly more in real life	-1.0530973	Slightly more in real life
26. In being shy and fond of being alone	-0.4603175	Slightly more in real life	-1.0884956	Slightly more in real life
27. In keeping their thoughts and feelings to themselves	-0.8015873	Slightly more in real life	-1.1681416	Slightly more in real life
28. In being self-aware	-0.7936508	Slightly more in real life	-0.7964602	Slightly more in real life
29. In being sensitive	-0.3650794	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.3451327	Generally the same in real life and online
30. In being quiet and lacking in confidence	-0.4444444	Slightly more in real life	-0.9911504	Slightly more in real life
Grand weighted mean	-0.5825397	Slightly more in real life	-0.8973451	Slightly more in real life

Table 5. Extroverted Behaviors

Item	Set A's Perception of of Self		Set B's Perception of Others	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
31. In being friendly, good-natured and easy to talk to	-0.4761905	Slightly more in real life	-0.4070796	Slightly more in real life
32. In displaying a pleasant manner to others	-0.5714286	Slightly more in real life	-0.6725664	Slightly more in real life
33. In being confident and forceful	-0.2619048	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.2743363	Generally the same in real life and online
34. In being commanding and respected	-0.3492063	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.6460177	Slightly more in real life
35. In exhibiting a compelling charm that inspires other people	-0.3174603	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.3274336	Generally the same in real life and online
36. In being enthusiastic	-0.4761905	Slightly more in real life	-0.4070796	Slightly more in real life
37. In being fond of	-0.4444444	Slightly more in	-0.3628319	Generally the same in

company and sociable		real life		real life and online
38. In being able to persuade or convince other people	-0.3730159	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.2920354	Generally the same in real life and online
39. In being self-assured	-0.6190476	Slightly more in real life	-0.7522124	Slightly more in real life
40. In being fond of making conversation with other people	-0.2936508	Generally the same in real life and online	-0.2212389	Generally the same in real life and online
Grand weighted mean	-0.418254	Slightly more in real life	-0.4362832	Slightly more in real life

Table 6. Comparison of Set A's Perception of Self and Set B's Perception of Others with respect to Positive Relationship Behaviors (Using Welch's t-test)

	Set A's Perception of Self	Set B's Perception of Others
Mean	-0.633	-0.520
Standard Deviation	0.556	0.664
N	126	114
Two-tailed P value: 0.1578		Not statistically significant

Table 7. Comparison of Set A's Perception of Self and Set B's Perception of Others with respect to Negative Relationship Behaviors (Using Welch's t-test)

	Set A's Perception of Self	Set B's Perception of Others
Mean	0.119	-0.063
Standard Deviation	0.559	0.756
N	126	114
Two-tailed P value: 0.0374		Statistically significant

Table 8. Comparison of Set A's Perception of Self and Set B's Perception of Others with respect to Introverted Behaviors (Using Welch's t-test)

	Set A's Perception of Self	Set B's Perception of Others
Mean	-0.583	-0.897
Standard Deviation	0.576	0.568
N	126	114
Two-tailed P value: < 0.0001		Extremely statistically significant

Table 9. Comparison of Set A's Perception of Self and Set B's Perception of Others with respect to Extroverted Behaviors (Using Welch's t-test)

	Set A's Perception of Self	Set B's Perception of Others
Mean	-0.418	-0.436
Standard Deviation	0.597	0.713
N	126	114
Two-tailed P value: 0.8334		Not statistically significant

DISCUSSION

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that respondents perceive the practice of Positive Relationship Behaviors as *slightly more in real life* in both themselves and in others.

However, it can be observed in Table 3 that the respondents perceive the practice of Negative Behaviors as *generally the same in real life and online* in both themselves and in others.

Looking at Table 4, the respondents perceive the practice of Introverted Behaviors as *slightly more in real life* in both themselves and in others.

And in Table 5, the respondents perceive the practice of Extroverted Behaviors as *slightly more in real life* in both themselves and in others.

However, when comparing the responses of Set A and Set B for Negative Behaviors (Table 7), a *statistically significant* difference was found. Furthermore, the difference in the responses of Set A and Set B for Introverted Behaviors (Table 8) was found to be *extremely statistically significant*.

These results imply that the respondents perceive their and other's real life and online behavior to be different when it comes to Positive Relationship Behaviors, Introverted Behaviors and Extroverted Behaviors and that in all three, they perceive their practice to be *slightly more in real life*.

Based on the foregoing, it would appear that there is some incongruity between real life and online behaviors of the respondents, as the Self-discrepancy Theory suggests.

As this study is limited by the number of respondents, the researcher recommends further investigation as well the inclusion of other types of behaviors to see whether or not individuals perceive their practice to vary between real life and online. Other factors could be considered and studied as to why such variation exists.

REFERENCES

- [1] Koeze, E., & Popper, N. (2020, April 7). *The virus changed the way we internet*. The New York Times. Retrieved September 22, 2021, from <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2020/04/07/technology/coronavirus-internet-use.html>.
- [2] Kristen Herhold / 17 October 2018. (n.d.). *How people use social media in 2018*. How People Use Social Media in 2018 | August 2021. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://themanifest.com/digital-marketing/how-people-use-social-media-2018>.
- [3] Pew Research Center. (2021, April 26). *Demographics of social media users and adoption in the United States*. Pew Research Center: Internet, Science & Tech. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/fact-sheet/social-media/>.
- [4] *The 10 top reasons why we use Social Networks*. WeRSM. (2018, October 17). Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://wersm.com/the-10-top-reasons-why-we-use-social-networks/>.
- [5] Hu, C., Kumar, S., Huang, J., & Ratnavelu, K. (2018, October 5). *How to better satisfy online users? A quantitative study of identity reconstruction based on advanced self-discrepancy theory*. AIP Publishing. Retrieved September 25, 2021, from <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/1.5062707>.
- [6] Schwartz, H. A., Eichstaedt, J. C., Kern, M. L., Dziurzynski, L., Ramones, S. M., Agrawal, M., Shah, A., Kosinski, M., Stillwell, D., Seligman, M. E. P., & Ungar, L. H. (n.d.). *Personality, gender, and age in the language of social media: The open-vocabulary approach*. PLOS ONE. Retrieved September 22, 2021, from <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0073791>.
- [7] *List of words that describe behavior*. Grammar. (n.d.). Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://grammar.yourdictionary.com/word-lists/list-of-words-that-describe-behavior.html>.